

Investigations to Overcome the Effects of Jamming

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Abstract: *Over the last 3 decades, wireless communication has become vital in providing a wide bandwidth. These days, voice, video, and data transfer have become essential. In wireless and RADAR communications, signal corruption masking has become a routine problem. Most often, these problems are due to intentional jamming. It is also evident that the above problems are also due to electromagnetic interference generated by manmade and natural sources. Although several researchers have reported different techniques in the open literature, no simple system is optimized. In view of these facts, an attempt is made in the present work to bring out some useful techniques by undertaking intensive investigations. In the present work, two typical methods are presented for effective communication overcoming the electromagnetic interference caused by intentional or unintentional jammers.*

1. Comprehensive Background:

Wireless communication plays a very important role in exchanging information. It provides services to improve the quality of human life. However, wireless communication takes place in an exposed nature (free space), so anyone can transmit the signal through the same medium. Due to the free space medium, attackers can intentionally interfere in particular channels (who want to disturb/block the communication). The intentional interference is called Jamming; it is unlike interference, which can be caused unintentionally. To make uninterrupted communication, we should avoid jamming. The techniques used for avoiding jamming are called anti-jamming techniques.

To overcome the problem of jamming, we should analyze different kinds of jamming techniques and know the countermeasures for it. So, we discuss some jamming and anti-jamming techniques; examples of jammers are proactive, reactive, function-specific, and hybrid-smart jammers. Then, dealing with the jamming problem requires more research; for instance, the simple solution is sending high transmitted power to make less threat of jamming, and one more is by using directional antennas instead of omnidirectional antennas.

- Section 2 deals with a typical jammer situation.
- Section 3 deals with proposed techniques for jamming and its countermeasures.

- Sections 4, 5 & 6 deal with results, conclusion & references.

2. A Typical Jammer Situation:

The basic jamming phenomenon and how the typical jammer will be introduced in radar communication are shown in the figures below.

Fig 1. Basic jamming phenomenon

Fig 2. Typical jammer

3. Proposed Techniques:

A jammer can have either the same or different capabilities in the network that is going to be attacked. The broad classification of jammers is elementary and advanced; elementary jammers are again subdivided into proactive and reactive, and advanced jammers can be divided into function-specific and smart hybrid (Int. J. Ad Hoc and Ubiquitous Computing).

3.1 Elementary Jammers

3.1.1 Proactive Jammer:

Jammer sends packets or random bits into the channel that are going to be attacked, and it does not switch the channel. Proactive jammers are constant, deceptive, and random.

Constant Jammer: It continuously sends random to the channel without observing the status of the channel, which means it will not observe whether communication is happening through the channel or not, and it makes the channel busy every time. Because of constantly sending bits, it is an inefficient technique but can be easily launched [1].

Deceptive jammer: It continuously transmits packets instead of random bits [1]. It is more difficult to identify this jammer because it sends packets. It is also energy inefficient because of continuous transmission but easy to launch.

Random jammer: it sends either packets or random bits but it does not send continuously. In the above two jammers, energy inefficiency is the drawback, so here, for energy saving, it switches between jamming and sleeping, which means it sends packets or random bits for certain time intervals, and it will be off for certain time intervals. At sleeping times, communication can happen, which means there is a tradeoff between energy efficiency and jamming efficiency. Here, there is a possibility of selecting the duration of the sleeping time interval and the duration of the jamming time interval. So that energy efficiency and jamming efficiency can be manageable [1].

3.1.2 Reactive Jammers:

These jammers transmit the signals after observing the network activity, which means the jammer must continuously monitor the channel activity

Reactive RTS/CTS jammer: before sending any information through the channel, the sender sends request-to-send (RTS). After sending the RTS bit, the jammer starts jamming, which means it stops sending RTS to the receiver, so the sender waits for clear-to-send (CTS) information from the receiver, but the receiver will send CTS because RTS is blocked, but the sender believes that the receiver may be busy. So, the sender will not send any information. Alternatively, jamming can be started after sending CTS to the sender. Here, the jammer blocks the information that is sent from the sender [2].

Reactive data /ACK jammer: jamming starts after sending information. It blocks the acknowledge signal from the receiver so the sender believes that the transmitted information has not reached the receivers; therefore, it continuously retransmits the information. This jammer can also corrupt the data packets [2].

3.2 Advanced jammers

3.2.1 Function Specific jammers:

It starts jamming with pre-determined functions. It can switch between channels for jamming, which means it can jam multiple channels, so jamming throughput is high.

Follow-on jammer: it jams multiple channels by following the channels, which means if the transmitter identifies that jamming is happening in a channel, it switches to another channel for transmission, but the jammer also switches to that channel by following the transmitter [3].

Pulsed noise jammer: it can jam multiple channels with different bandwidths at times. It is also like an elementary random jammer, switches the sleeping time period and jamming time period according to scheduled programming, but it can attack multiple channels [4].

3.2.2 Smart Hybrid Jammers:

These jammers can be implemented with either proactive or reactive, so-called hybrid jammers, and these are energy efficient and power efficient, so-called smart. These can spend sufficient energy in required places and not in unwanted places for energy management.

3.3 Jamming Detection and Countermeasures:

As jamming is very harmful to communication, avoiding jamming is very important. Anti-jamming can be found by calculating signal-to-noise ratio, bit error rate, packet transmission rate, etc... If jamming is detected in a channel, the sender must change the channel from where the jamming is happening. Some of the jamming detection is explained as follows.

JAM (Jammed Area Mapping protocol): it calculates the threshold for node utility of a channel. If the threshold value is higher, then it believes that there is a jammer in the channel. According to that, it sends messages like jammed or unjammed. If it is jammed, then JAM starts countermeasures by providing a different route for communication after the mapping process [5].

Ant Systems: It collects information from the channel and stores it to calculate BER, SNR, and PDR metrics. According to these values, it can identify whether a jammer existed or not [4].

Hybrid system: This anti-jamming system works by combining three techniques: 1. Base station replication means multiple base stations of the same type available in a network, base station evasion means withdrawing of base station if jamming is observed, and multipath routing means multiple data routes will be presented between nodes and base station [6].

Channel surfing and spatial retreat: when it detects a jammer in a channel, it shifts communication to another channel, spatial retreat means it moves nodes from one place to another place for a safe location [7].

Reactive-jamming detection using BER: it keeps received signal strength (RSS) is low. After receiving bits, it calculates the bit error rate for every single bit; if errors are more after calculating BER using error correcting codes due to weak signal, the RSS should be low, and if errors are caused by high RSS, it can identify signals have interfered from jammer [8].

- In the present paper, it is of interest to consider new proposed techniques to escape from intentional jamming in RADAR communication [9].

1. When a wide pulse is transmitted from the radar for the detection of multiple targets, which are radially the same distance from the source. The received eco's are bound to overlap. As a result, it becomes difficult to know whether there is one object or more objects. In this situation, it is possible to send very narrow pulses, so that the received eco's are distinct. This type of situation is presented in Fig 3.

Fig 3. Effect of broad pulses

2. When the radar transmitter is operated at low power, the received eco's are completely masked by the noise or jamming signal or electromagnetic interference (EMI), as shown fig4. To overcome this problem, the transmitter power is sufficiently enhanced to appear beyond the noise threshold.

Fig 4. Effect of transmitter power

3. when the radiated beam is very broad, it illuminates more targets, which are radially at the same distance again; the echo's will reach the radar display at the same time, and it appears as a single pulse. This results in the problem of discrimination of multiple targets. In order to overcome these and improve target detection, the radar beam is made very narrow, and it is scanned if necessary. This situation is presented in figure 5.

Fig 5.Effect of broad beam

4. Results:

The proposed anti-jamming and anti-EMI techniques are extremely useful in overcoming EMI problems and improving communication between friendly aircraft and friendly communication systems.

5. Conclusions:

The radiation of narrow pulses, the design of high-power radar transmitters, and the generation of narrow beams are found to yield excellent results where the perfect effect of jamming is nullified.

6. References:

- [1] Xu W, Trappe W, Zhang Y, Wood T (2005) The feasibility of launching and detecting jamming attacks in wireless networks. In: Proceedings of the 6th ACM International Symposium on Mobile Ad Hoc Networking and Computing, pp 46–57
- [2] Pelechrinis K, Iliofotou M, Krishnamurthy S (2011) Denial of service attacks in wireless networks: The case of jammers. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials* 13(2):245–257
- [3] Mpitzopoulos A, Gavalas D, Konstantopoulos C, Pantziou G (2009) A survey on jamming attacks and countermeasures in WSNs. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials* 11(4):42–56
- [4] Muraleedharan R, Osadciw LA (2006) Jamming attack detection and countermeasures in wireless sensor network using ant system. In: SPIE the International Society for Optical Engineering, vol 6248, p 62480G
- [5] Wood A, Stankovic J, Son S (2003) JAM: a jammed-area mapping service for sensor networks. In: 24th IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium, pp 286–297
- [6] Jain SK, Garg K (2009) A hybrid model of defense techniques against base station jamming attack in wireless sensor networks. In: Proceedings of the 2009 First International Conference on Computational Intelligence, Communication Systems and Networks, pp 102–107
- [7] Xu W, Wood T, Trappe W, Zhang Y (2004) Channel surfing and spatial retreats: defenses against wireless denial of service. In: Proceedings of the 3rd ACM Workshop on Wireless Security, pp 80–89
- [8] Strasser M, Danev B, Capkun S (2010) Detection of reactive jamming in sensor networks. *ACM Transactions on Sensor Networks* 7(2):16:1–16:29
- [9] Basic Radar (MC Graw-hill 198).